

**THE VALUE OF FORMING BASIC COMPETENCES IN
THE PROCESS OF PREPARING PRESCHOOL
CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION**

Kholtorayeva Sabina

Department of Preschool Education
Methodology of TDPU named after Nizomi teacher

Ramzonova Bahoroy

Department of Preschool Education
Methodology of TDPU named after Nizomi teacher

***Annotation:** Today, the main goal of pre-school education organizations is to prepare children for school in a comprehensive manner and to develop them harmoniously. In order to improve the quality of preschool education, it is necessary to prepare the child for school from an early age, to integrate basic competencies, and to adopt a modern approach to pedagogical and psychological processes. Key words: Child, preschool education, competence, social-emotional, communicative, personal, knowledge, development, value, result, efficiency.*

Today, foreign experiences show the need to provide conditions for choosing life directions in the formation of preschool children as individuals. In developed countries, attention and investment in education has proven to be the most important factor in strengthening the state. Understanding that the preschool period is a unique social and cultural phenomenon, and its impact on a child's life creates a solid foundation for the rest of his life is considered an urgent problem.

In accordance with the trends of innovative development in the field of education in the world, special attention is paid to the improvement of the pre-school education

system based on competency requirements. In particular, the development of creative technologies aimed at increasing the psychophysiological, intellectual, creative and personal potential of children on a global scale, the organization of an innovative educational environment in preschool education organizations, and the improvement of the quality mechanisms of preschool education based on the principles of strategic management focused scientific and practical research is being carried out.

Information on the management of preschool education in these studies Methodical improving the system, diversifying quality education services, introducing information and communication technologies, interactive and problem-based teaching methods into the educational process, implementing effective forms and methods of developing and evaluating professional innovative competence of preschool education system pedagogues special attention is paid to the issues of Currently, in our country, special attention is paid to the field of preschool education, and large-scale work is being carried out in this regard.

The formation of basic competencies of preschool children lays the groundwork for them to study in school without difficulty in the future. The main competences of the child are communicative, social competence, knowledge, personal competence.

Communicative competence - requires having constructive methods and means of interaction with people around; the ability to communicate and successfully solve the game, cognitive, household and creative tasks that arise. This competence includes the development of speech.

Social competence is a child's ability to work together with peers and adults, observing the established order and etiquette. Children learn to respect others and take into account what they have to say.

Personal competence (creating the concept of "I"). By developing personal competence, the child is at preschool age exhibits a number of characteristics that are formed and improved throughout its life. This competency includes the child's ability to take responsibility for self-care and the skills to manage daily life and practice a sustainable healthy lifestyle.

Cognitive competence includes the ability to acquire knowledge, read and learn, independently search, analyze and select the necessary information to understand the environment. Therefore, in the process of preparing children for school education, it is important to form basic competencies in an integrated manner.

In many psychological and pedagogical literature, the concept of "readiness for school" is a characteristic feature of the development of a person as a person, it is expressed by the scale of psychological, psycho-mental characteristics in a child, without which it is impossible to successfully master educational activities at school.

According to V.V.Davidov, "readiness for school is a set of morphophysiological and psychological characteristics of an older preschool child, the systematic organization of which ensures a successful transition to school."

The main goals and objectives of the competence approach in preschool education are determined as a result of:

1) value - the acquisition and manifestation of competence occurs in the process of mastering the content of preschool education;

2) the goal - when competence combines the development of intelligence and skills (knowledge, skills, abilities, experience, relationships), education implementation of socialization and individualization.;

3) the resulting competence includes a number of skills (communicative, informational, language, social, personal, etc.) that are close to each other in the field of action and activity.

Personality development of preschool children is the whole life of a preschool child and his further education considered as an important basis for In the process of school preparation, it is very important to form the communicative, socio-cultural, knowledge, and personal competence of the children, which are considered the initial competences necessary for the child to live in the society, and guarantee that the children will go to the school education process without problems in the future.

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